

Study on Body Positioning of Haptic Feedback in Simulated Human-Robot Cooperative Tasks

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Abstract—In this abstract, we present our preliminary studies toward the determination of a possible body position suitable for haptic feedback devices. Preliminary works on this topic have demonstrated the efficacy of haptic feedback to display to the user possible task information. However, for most of these signals a clear somatotopic mapping is not defined and previous researches present a set of possible solutions ranging from vibrating rings to bracelets and other devices. Here we investigate skin stretch as a possible haptic stimulus and we perform a user study considering three possible locations for the feedback.

I. INTRODUCTION

Humans and robots are expected to collaborate in the next future since the technology readiness level of devices are advanced enough to make robots part of our everyday life [1], [2]. One of the key aspects in integrating human and robot seems to be the possibility of the robot to feedback task information to the user companion through haptic interfaces [3], [4]. However, on several occasions, it is not clear where is the best body location to feedback task information. For instance, in [3] a vibrating ring is used to alert the human operator about the estimation of the position of the operators' hand. However, in the literature, there are no studies that describe which is the best location for a feedback device in a generic human-robot cooperative task, where a clear somatotopic matching cannot be established. Authors studied spatial discrimination in some restricted parts of the body such as the head [5] or explored how the softness could be perceived in a teleoperation scenario [6], but never trying to explore the effect of the haptic feedback in different parts of the body. In this work, we investigate the possibility that positioning the same haptic feedback in different places of the body could make a difference in the performance or preference of subjects while performing a collaborative task. The goal of this experiment is to understand if there is a user preferred area among three body locations, shoulder, wrist, and hip where the continuous haptic feedback improves the performance in a simulated human-robot cooperative task. The three locations were chosen to not interfere with task execution. We also considered an interface that can measure the shoulder flexion/extension as possible input for the collaborative tasks. We considered the shoulder motion as a part of the body that is not directly involved in the task.

Fig. 1. In the top figure, the skin stretch device is secured to the wrist of a user. In the bottom figure, the GUI is shown.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The experimental setup consists of two parts integrated to work with a graphical user interface implemented in LabView: The input device, whose aim is to track the shoulder inclination in real-time, and the feedback devices, that are in charge of providing continuous haptic feedback to the user. The cooperative task is represented by a reaching task, simulated as a goal zone in a bar visualised on a screen. Extremes of the horizontal bar are the limits of inclination of the shoulder. The user has to lift up or down the shoulder, which is tracked by means of the aforementioned accelerometer, to reach a goal inclination. The GUI, which is shown in Fig.1, represents the instantaneous inclination of the shoulder by filling the bar, in this way the user can check the current inclination and go towards the goal range of inclination, which is a sub-range of the whole range of motion. The role of the haptic feedback is to inform the user of the relative inclination of the shoulder with respect to the whole range of motion. The range of motion is acquired at the beginning of the experiment during the calibration phase. Six users underwent the experiment, consisting of 120 repetitions of the reaching task, 30 times by four feedback conditions: feedback on the shoulder, feedback on the wrist, feedback on the hip, and no feedback.

The input to the system is an instrumented back brace, which can estimate the inclination of the shoulder. The device

Fig. 2. Exploded view of the device assembly. The pale yellow part represents the part of the two solid cylinders which are in contact with the subject.

consists of a commercial back brace posture corrector, upon which was placed an ADXL362 accelerometer, a Teensy 3.2 microcontroller, and an RN42 Bluetooth antenna. Accelerometer signals are buffered and further processed in LabVIEW. We calibrated the accelerometer by following the procedure described in [7]. To estimate the inclination of the shoulder we used the roll of the accelerometer as:

$$\theta_{roll} = \frac{180}{\pi} \cdot \tan \left(\frac{G_y}{\sqrt{G_x^2 + G_z^2}} \right) \quad (1)$$

Where $G_{x,y,z}$ are the readings of the accelerometer, which we consider to be very close to the gravitational force on the three axes. To calibrate the inclination sensor for each participant, at the beginning of each experiment we asked participants to raise the shoulder as high as possible while sitting in a comfortable position. We did the same for the low shoulder position and used these roll readings as the working range of the device. The users then had direct control of a bar which fills up proportionally to the estimated roll in the range. To provide continuous haptic feedback to the users we implemented a wearable skin stretch device inspired by that used in [8]. The device stretches the skin by rotating two equally spaced solid disks around their middle point. All parts were 3D-printed except for the motor, the screws, and the elastic bands. The electronics consist of an esp-8266 microcontroller which can receive broadcast WiFi messages with a latency lower than 10 milliseconds. To set the position of the skin stretch device the only command is to set the servomotor position. A detailed view of the internals of the device is shown in Fig. 2.

III. RESULTS

To evaluate the performance of subjects, we collected the time to reach the target, measured as the time which elapses between the beginning of the task and the first time at which the user enters in the goal range. Results show no significant difference between feedback placement in terms of time to reach the target ($p < 0.523$) as shown in Fig. 3. Furthermore, we gave subjects a 5-Point Likert Scale [9] questionnaire to have a qualitative measure of user preferences. All subjects selected “Agree” to the sentence “The haptic feedback has been useful to complete the task”. On the contrary, to the sentences “I found the haptic feedback placed in the hip/wrist/shoulder helpful to complete the task” preferences

Fig. 3. One-way ANOVA performed for recorded times to reach the target.

of subjects changes. None of the participants agreed on the usefulness of the hip feedback, all participants “Agreed” on the wrist feedback usefulness, and for the shoulder 50% percent of the participants “Agreed” and the other 50% percent “Strongly agreed” on its helpfulness.

IV. CONCLUSION

From these preliminary results based on user performance and replies to the questionnaires there is no evidence that one of the selected locations is better than the others. It seems that feedback is important for task execution but that location of feedback does not influence performance in the human-robot interaction suggesting that, considering three locations with similar skin condition, skin receptors plays the mayor role. We are currently considering different haptic stimuli, for example using vibrating motors, to understand if by changing the type of stimulated skin receptors we can appreciate some statistical difference in performance between different body locations.

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